

EXPLORING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIRECT MARKETING

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ABSTRACT

The study sheds light on the process of direct marketing and its impacts on the performance of business companies. In the present time, the technological implementation plays most effective role to develop business management. Apart from that, the concept of artificial intelligence and business management in the business organization is also analyzed in this particular research study. This research study has discussed the effectiveness of business management through implementation of technologies. This, organizing, planning, and analyzing are the major parts of business management. In addition to that, artificial intelligence is a type of **modern technology** that works based on software.

On the other hand, the researcher has used several types of research methods for understanding the concept of the topic. Apart from that, the researcher has used **secondary qualitative data collection method** for collecting data about the research topic and analysing the data. Thereafter, the researcher has used the **positivism research philosophy** and descriptive research design for understanding the concept of business management, artificial intelligence, and direct marketing. Along with that, the researcher has adopted the secondary methods for gathering more accurate and genuine information about the impacts of artificial intelligence and business management on direct marketing. Thus, the researcher has used the qualitative methods for analysing all the data in a **thematic way** in this particular research study. The business organization has implemented big data analysis and industry 4.0 technologies to improve the organizational performance.

Keywords: *Advance technology, business management, Big data analysis, Chatbot.*

INTRODUCTION

Business management is a process of learning about business activities that are focused on three different steps. Thus, the steps are organizing then planning, and then analyzing. Therefore, the beneficial sites of these steps of business management are analyzed in this particular research study. Apart from that, artificial intelligence is technology-based software that helps companies in different sectors. Thereafter, the usage of artificial intelligence in several sectors of business companies helps in the development of those sectors. Furthermore, artificial intelligence can be used in producing products, advertising, supply chain management, and other sectors of business companies.

On the other hand, there are a lot of beneficial sites of business management and artificial intelligence for business organizations. Thus, the concept of business management and artificial intelligence and its usage in business organizations is analyzed in this particular research study. Therefore, the purpose of this particular research study is to analyze the impacts of business management and artificial intelligence on the direct marketing process. Furthermore, the concept of direct marketing and its impact on business organizations are also analyzed in this particular research study. Apart from that, the impacts of the direct marketing process on the financial performance of business organizations are also analyzed in this particular research study.

Overview of business management and Artificial intelligence in direct marketing

Direct marketing strategy has helped to enhance personal relationships among the customers and marketing organizations. Direct marketing has established effective communication between the customers and the marketing organization. This effective communication has enhanced the business in the marketplace. In the business management process, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the most effective aspect that increases the marketing performance of the organization. AI is an advanced technological application that builds an interconnected network with marketing organizations. Advanced technology has provided competitive advantages to the business organization [1]. In the present time, AI has played the most crucial role to develop the production and service quality of the organization. In the business management process, technological development has helped to mitigate the customer demand and attracted the customers towards the organization successfully. In the management process, AI has increased the growth of the organization and gets more benefits from the marketplace. The AI application has improved the organizational function through the implementation of better quality technology and innovation to analyze the business data and analyze the competition in the marketplace.

Importance of business management and Artificial intelligence in direct marketing

In the marketplace, the business organization plays various roles to provide effective services to the customers. Effective business management and AI have impacted the organization positively to enhance its growth of the organization. In the current business process, market competition is one of the most significant aspects that can reduce organizational growth in the marketplace. In this regard, the organization needs to improve its business performance through technological implementation.

Identification of sectors	Market Share
IT services	41.1%
Retail	5 %
Telecom	2.2%
Automotive	2.1

Table 1: Use of AI technology in various sectors
(Source: Influenced by [4])

In business management, AI has provided a competitive advantage to the organization. The **Big data analysis** and **Industry 4.0** technology has helped the organization to improve their performance through collect vast amount data [2]. In the business process, customer satisfaction is another most effective aspect. AI technology has increased organizational potentiality through effective technological implementation. At the present time, **80% of business organizations** have used the AI application in their business management process to develop organizational performance. AI technology has made 79% of work easier and flexible along with providing options for 75% for new ventures to flourish and usage of 59% of big data within the organization [2].

Figure 1: AI application in business organization
(Source: [2])

METHODOLOGY

In the research study, the methodology is the most effective aspect that increases the significance of the study. The methodology is divided into two parts one is primary and another is secondary research method. In the research study, primary data has been used in a case study-based research, and secondary data have used all types of research study. The data collection method is the most important aspect that helps to increase the relevance of the study. This research study has adopted the **secondary qualitative data collection method** to find the authentic result of this study. The researcher has collected secondary data from online sources. In this research study, the researcher has collected qualitative data and information from online journals, articles, books, and authentic websites [3]. In this research study, the researcher has adopted **thematic analysis** to interpret the secondary qualitative data. The research philosophy is the most effective aspect that

helps to complete this study successfully. This research study has adopted indicative philosophy to increase the value of this study. **Inductive philosophy** has analyzed the qualitative data and helps others to understand the importance of this study. In a research study, the research design is the other most significant aspect that helps to describe the actual findings of this study. In research methodology, reliability and validation play the most important role to increase the significance of this study. The reliability and validation have ensured that this study has followed appropriate data collection methods and data analysis techniques in this study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING

Role of business management and Artificial intelligence in direct marketing

Identification of AI markets	Revenue
Global AI market	327.5bn USD
AI software market	247.6bn USD
AI patent ownership	International Business Machines (IBM)

Table 1: Identification of AI markets

(Source: Influenced by [3])

Business management plays the most crucial role to develop organizational performance in the marketplace. The business organization has provided several different types of services to the customers. In this regard, the business organization needs to develop its function through technological implementation. In the business management process, AI applications have improved the product and service quality of the organization [4]. In the present time, customer satisfaction is one of the most effective aspects that can develop organizational performance in the marketplace. AI application has implemented advanced technology to business processes to collect the data from the marketplace. In business organizations, the AI application has collected vast amounts of data from the marketplace to analyze the customer's preference. Moreover, in the business process, AI applications have improved the communication between the business organization and customers that can improve the organizational function in the marketplace.

The AI application has helped to interact with the customers effectively. In the marketplace, the business organization can enhance their business by understanding the customer's preference. With the AI application, the organization can interact with 12 people at a time. This effective communication system has affected the customers positively. Moreover, this advanced technology has helped to understand the customer's preference in the marketplace, and the organization also changed their product and service quality through the implementation of these advanced technologies in the marketplace [5]. In the present time, most of the business organizations have used this AI application in their business management to improve their performance in the marketplace such as Reliance Industries, Tata steel organizations, and other popular business organizations have used this application to improve their performance.

Effects of Artificial intelligence in business organization

In the business process, AI technology has enhanced the performance of the organization. In the present time, the AI application has been used in most business organizations to grow their business in the marketplace. In the current business process, competition has increased significantly, for this reason, the organization needs to take effective technologies to improve their performance. In this regard, AI technologies have collected data from other companies and it has helped to analyze the performance of other organizations [6]. The AI application analyzes the data and through advanced technologies. This technological implementation has given the idea of the organization to know about the strength of competitors. According to this analysis, the organization can understand its weakness in the production process.

Reasons for adopting AI

Why is your organization interested in AI?

Percentage of respondents who somewhat or strongly agree with each statement

Figure 2: Effects of Artificial intelligence in business organization

(Source: [6])

The business organization can move to another new business through the AI application. On the other hand, the business organization has reduced its cost with the implementation of advanced technologies in its business process. At the present time, **55%** of businesses are AI-oriented because of improving the efficiency of the organization. At present, the business organization has used Big data analysis tools and industry 4.0 technology to analyze the customer data. In the marketplace, the business organization can predict the customer's preference through the AI application. This application analyzes the customer's preference in the marketplace and based on this analysis the organization can improve its product quality to serve the customers. Reliance Industries has used AI chatbots to communicate with customers. AI application has helped these industries to understand the customer's preference and retain the customers for the long term.

Positive impact of business management and Artificial intelligence in direct marketing

In the business management process, the AI application is the most effective aspect that helps the organization to develop more in the marketplace. In business organizations, AI applications have

helped to satisfy the costume's demand in the marketplace. This technological application has helped to communicate with the customers effectively through the chatbot and other advanced technology. In the present time, most business organizations have adopted this advanced technology to improve their performance in the marketplace [7]. At the present time, the Tata steel industry has used the AI application to improve its performance in the marketplace. This industry has solved **60-70%** of problems through advanced technological applications [8]. On the other hand, with this technological implementation, the organization has improved its product and service quality in the marketplace.

Figure 3: Positive impact of business management and Artificial intelligence
(Source: [7])

In the last two years, this organization has made a profit of **1000 crore** through the implementation of AI technology [8]. This AI application has helped to collect vast amounts of data from the marketplace to understand the strengthening of other organizations in the marketplace. In business organizations, the product and service quality has impacted the organization significantly. In this regard, the AI application has helped to collect the preference of the customers, and based on this analysis the organization can improve the product quality and get more profit from the marketplace.

CONCLUSION

After all these discussions, it can be concluded that the business organization has adopted effective business management and AI applications to improve its performance. The AI application has helped to collect vast amounts of data from the marketplace and analyze this data to get an idea about competitors. Moreover, this AI application has provided effective communication with costumes and that can help to understand the preference of the customers in the marketplace, and the organization has got the chance to improve their product according to the customer's demand.

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